

ARK PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS: AFFORDABLE LONG-TERM CITATION AND ACCESS

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Abstract – This half-day tutorial builds on the rapidly growing Archival Resource Key (ARK) as a flexible, affordable, yet long-established alternative persistent identifier (PID). At 24-years-old, the non-paywalled ARK identifier scheme is widely used for long-term access to cultural and scientific information, with accelerating adoption by small publishers, by under-resourced institutions, and in the global South. By the end of the tutorial, attendees will know when ARKs are appropriate to use and how to create them within their respective memory organizations. No prior experience is required.

Submission Type – Tutorial

Keywords – Identification, Preservation Planning, Policy, Metadata, Costs

Conference Topics – Haerenga – Journey

I. INTRODUCTION

Archival Resource Key (ARK) [1][2] identifiers help web users and content providers combat the commonly observed fragility of web addresses (URLs). The average lifetime of a URL was once said to be 100 days [3]. At the end of its life, a URL link breaks, usually giving you the dreaded "404 Not Found" error that most of us have seen. Irritating at best, it's a minor disaster for memory organizations.

In some ways ARKs are like DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers), URNs (Uniform Resource Names), and Handles. They have all been in use for over 24 years, they exist in large numbers (8.2 billion ARKs, 250 million DOIs, etc.), they are all repaired by vigilant updating of URL redirects, they support research and scholarship, and they appear in such places as the

Data Citation Index, Wikipedia, and ORCID.org profiles.

In contrast, ARKs come with no fees, no limits on how many you can create, and no metadata requirements. From the outset, ARKs were designed to be decentralized and to identify any kind of thing, whether digital, physical, or abstract. They are created by over 1500 ARK organizations, including 10 national libraries, 185 universities, 209 archives, 104 museums, and 101 journals.

II. TUTORIAL FORMAT

This 3-hour event (two 90-minute blocks) is intended for in-person and/or remote participation.

The tutorial is aimed for learners who directly or indirectly manage workflows of objects used in digital libraries. The target audience includes people engaged in creating, publishing, and processing web-referenceable objects from any domain in the sciences, humanities, education, law, etc. Typical attendees will be affiliated with museums, archives, libraries, data centers, and government agencies. No prior experience is required.

III. OBJECTIVES AND TOPICS

Attendees will learn when this highly flexible scheme is appropriate to use and how to create ARKs within their respective memory organizations.

The following topics will be covered.

- Why ARKs – non-paywalled, decentralized, and flexible

- Use cases – Smithsonian, French National Library, Internet Archive, Frick Collection
 - Metadata for early and ongoing object development
 - How to get started – one form to fill out
 - Minting and assigning ARK identifiers
 - Resolvers, resolution, redirection
 - Metadata for persistence and other vocabulary terms
 - Object types – digital, physical, conceptual
- Persistence considerations
 - Available tools

I. REFERENCES

- [1] The ARK Alliance. <https://arks.org/>.
- [2] Kunze, John. 2003. *Towards Electronic Persistence Using ARK Identifiers*. <https://n2t.net/ark:/13030/c7n00zt1z>.
- [3] Taylor, Nicholas. November 2011. *The Average Lifespan of a Webpage*. <https://blogs.loc.gov/thesignal/2011/11/the-average-lifespan-of-a-webpage/>.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

John Kunze is a pioneer in the theory and practice of digital libraries. A former Berkeley Unix hacker, he created the ARK persistent identifier scheme, led publication of the BagIt, WARC, and Dublin Core standards, and wrote the formal recommendations that moved the first URL standard (which had stalled) across the finish line.

Donny Winston works to make research organizations more effective by shifting data management practices from a lumpy, bibliographic model to a more fine-grained, query-oriented engineering model. Via GupriDB ApS, which he co-founded, he is building the research information system for angry nerds: a FAIR, decentralized, no-vendor-lock-in research data management, assessment, and knowledge organization system.

